

ISic1461

I.Sicily inscription 1461

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

tuff

(yellow)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance

Locality of 'Piana'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8805

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. οἴμοι ὃ Εὐρυφῶν

2. ἡ Ἀρχιδίδα

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284906

EDR 112553

EDCS 41300079

EDCS 64800253

PHI 175693

Bibliography

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